

ANALYSIS OF THE ONGOING REFORMS IN THE INVESTIGATIVE SERVICE OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада муаллиф томонидан сўнгги йилларда ички ишлар органлари тергов хизматида амалга оширилган ислохотлар хусусан шахсинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини ишончли ҳимоя қилиш, тергов соҳасига ахборот технологиялари, халқаро стандартлар ва илғор хорижий тажрибани жорий этиш каби бир қатор ислохотлар ўрганилиб таҳлил қилинган. Таҳлил асосида тегишли хулосалар қилинган.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье исследован и проанализирован ряд реформ, проведенных автором в последние годы в следственной службе органов внутренних дел, в частности надежная защита прав и свобод личности, внедрение в сферу расследования информационных технологий, международных стандартов и передового зарубежного опыта. На основании анализа были сделаны соответствующие выводы.

ANNOTATION

This article examines and analyzes a number of reforms carried out by the author in recent years in the investigative service of the internal affairs bodies, in particular, reliable protection of personal rights and freedoms, the introduction of information technologies, international standards and advanced foreign experience into the field of investigation. Based on the analysis, the relevant conclusions were drawn.

Калит сўзлар: тергов, тергов бўлинмалари, ахборот технологиялари, ички ишлар органлари, ҳуқуқ ва эркинликлар.

Ключевые слова: следствие, следственные подразделения, информационные технологии, органы внутренних дел, права и свободы человека.

Keywords: investigation, investigative units, information technology, internal affairs agencies, human rights and freedoms.

It is known that a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other inalienable rights and freedoms are considered sacred and guaranteed by the State by law.

Over the past period, many changes and additions have been made to criminal legislation in our country aimed at liberalizing the system of criminal penalties, in particular, differentiation and individualization of responsibility, expansion of alternative types of punishment to imprisonment.

Only when the rule of law is ensured will the idea of “for the sake of human dignity” be fully reflected in our lives. It is expected that the Oliy Majlis and the Message of the Head of our country to the people of Uzbekistan will serve to radically improve the lives of our people.

The main goal of this message is to ensure the protection of human rights by improving legislation in any way. Indeed, human value begins with freedom, and the fruit of our reforms

in recent years also reflects the image of humanity. This appeal set the highest priorities in many areas, including taking another important step towards judicial and legal reform.

In general, in subsequent years, the reforms of the internal affairs system also acquired a dynamic character, in connection with which many decrees, resolutions and departmental normative legal acts were adopted. Concepts and programs have been developed and implemented.

In particular, in order to reliably protect individual rights and freedoms, introduce information technologies, international standards and advanced foreign experience in the field of investigation, a number of reforms were carried out in the investigative service.

In particular, a working group of industry specialists has been formed in the Investigative Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, a modern methodology for investigating crimes related to fraud, illicit trafficking in psychotropic substances, human trafficking and theft in a widespread virtual space has been developed and put into practice.

Since September 2021, an “innovative virtual Investigative polygon” has been created in all territorial investigative departments, which is now being effectively used to enhance the experience of investigators and interrogators.

During court sessions, investigators and interrogators acquire appropriate skills in understanding and eliminating shortcomings that may be made during the investigation.

In order to identify the causes of crimes and the conditions that allow them, prevent crimes, reduce the risk of turning citizens into victims and increase their legal awareness and legal culture, the Investigative

Department and units of subordinate investigative bodies conduct open dialogues and meetings in mahallas and educational institutions. In order to increase the professional potential of employees, the Ministry adopted a resolution dated March 30, 2021 “On measures to further improve the system of continuous professional development of employees of investigative departments of internal affairs bodies”.

The Investigative Department has organized weekly Saturday training sessions in videoconference mode with the participation of territorial divisions, while on Fridays and Saturdays of the week, the Investigative Department conducts training sessions for 30 young investigators and interrogators of the republic.

In continuation of the reforms, in order to train qualified personnel in the field of crime investigation, Decree No. UP257 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 28, 2022 “On the introduction of a qualitatively new system of training qualified personnel in the field of crime investigation” was adopted.

This Decree establishes that investigators and interrogators are trained at the law enforcement Academy in courses of professional retraining, professional retraining and advanced training in the form of primary specialization.

We are now living in a turbulent information age. Today, it is necessary for the information services of government agencies to become a leading force in providing people with timely and reliable information.

Based on these requirements, the official website has been launched “Tergov.uz” Facebook Instagram and Telegram social media pages have been opened on the you tube website, and direct communication with individuals and legal entities has been established. At

the same time, a new platform has been created that can communicate directly electronically with the head of the investigation department.

Through this system, a direct transparent dialogue with citizens is established, most importantly, vagrancy of citizens is prevented. In order to organize the participation of suspects and accused persons held in pre-trial detention facilities in investigative actions through a video conferencing system together with the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, investigative units were connected to the video conferencing platform provided by UZTELECOM JSC.

Thus, the practice of participation of suspects and accused persons held in pre-trial detention facilities in investigative actions through a video conferencing system has been established.

In addition, cases of application of procedural coercion measures that restrict individual rights are included in the unified electronic accounting system. The introduction of this system into practice made it possible to keep electronic records of the application of procedural coercion measures to suspects or accused persons that restrict their rights, and monitor them online.

In recent years, significant work has been carried out in our country to introduce modern information technologies in the judicial and legal sphere. In particular, thanks to the digitalization of the activities of judicial and law enforcement agencies, their openness and transparency have been ensured, and close cooperation has been established with civil society institutions, the media and the general public.

In order to further digitalize investigative activities and establish a unified electronic document management system in pre-trial case management, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-105 "On measures to introduce a unified system of interdepartmental electronic interaction in pre-trial case management" was adopted.

In accordance with the resolution, an operational information exchange has been established between 29 State bodies and organizations to ensure prompt receipt of information necessary for the consideration of applications, reports and other information about crimes at the stage of pre-trial proceedings in the case and conducting an inquiry and preliminary investigation in a criminal case.

These reforms are designed to raise the activities of the investigative units of the internal affairs bodies to a qualitatively new level. Currently, the internal affairs bodies are training, retraining and advanced training of investigators and interrogators, taking into account the personnel of investigative units and the weight of criminal cases, as well as further improving the effectiveness of the activities of internal affairs bodies to investigate crimes:

- to contribute to the improvement of the knowledge of investigators and interrogators in the field of information technology, the widespread introduction of specialized training programs on the methodology of disclosure and investigation of cybercrimes, acceleration of training in these areas;

- continuation of the construction of additional special premises in investigative units equipped with audio and video recording systems of investigative actions;

- travel to the regions, critically review the investigation and investigation process and study the positive experience and apply it in other regions;

- considering that the bulk of the personnel of the investigative units are young employees, improving their professional and practical skills through distance learning of employees using a video conferencing system implemented between the Investigative Department and its territorial divisions, as well as involving relevant specialists directly in the territorial investigative departments;

- further acceleration of direct dialogue with citizens, a sharp reduction in the number of appeals by timely and prompt provision of appropriate explanations on issues of interest to them;

- The main goal is to prepare and introduce draft laws in accordance with the established procedure to eliminate gaps and contradictions in legislation and improve criminal, criminal procedure and administrative legislation.

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